

Crystal structure of zinc(II) complex with thiosemicarbazone of acetone

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Manuscript received 30 August 1999, accepted 26 November 1999

Synthesis and crystal structure determination of the title complex are presented. It shows that the zinc atom located in the distorted tetrahedral coordination, is composed of two nitrogen atoms and two sulfur atoms from the two ligands.

The thiosemicarbazide and thiosemicarbazones have attracted special attention due to their activity against viruses, protozoa small pox and certain kinds of tumour¹ since Domagk's original discovery² of their antitubercular activity. It is known that some drugs have increased activity when administered as metal complexes³ and a number of metal chelates inhibit tumour growth⁴. In cancer treatment it has been shown that the active species is not the thiosemicarbazone itself but a metal chelate of the thiosemicarbazone⁵. After Mashima's work⁶ coordination chemists also took interest in thiosemicarbazide and thiosemicarbazone as potential ligands⁷. Further, zinc plays a vital role in biological processes. Hence, it was thought worthwhile to study the complexation with divalent zinc. We report here the preparation and crystal structure of zinc(II) complex with thiosemicarbazone of acetone (Hatsc).

Results and Discussion

The complex has a distorted tetrahedral geometry with approximate C_2 symmetry. The crystal structure contains three crystallographically independent molecules of which Zn 1 and Zn 2 are identical within error limits, they and Zn 3 exhibit mirror difference in geometry. Views of the three

Fig. 1. Crystal structure of $[Zn(atsc)_2]$ showing the atom labelling for three independent molecules.

molecules of $[Zn(atsc)_2]$ are shown with their atom labelling (Fig. 1). Bond lengths and angles are given in Table 1. For the compounds the lattice contains discrete molecules without any intermolecular interaction. The acetone thiosemicarbazonato ligands are clearly unianionic bidentate with N and S as coordinate atoms. The bond angle at zinc shows considerable distortion from regular tetrahedral geometry due to the small bite angle N–Zn–S of the acetone thiosemicarbazonato ligand, with the range 86.64–87.72° for 1, 86.85–86.96° for 2 and 86.51–87.00° for 3.

Table 1. Selected lengths (Å) and angles (°) for $[Zn(atsc)_2]$

Molecule	1	Molecule	2	Molecule	3
Zn(1)-S(1)	2.2891(8)	Zn(2)-S(3)	2.2687(8)	Zn(3)-S(5)	2.2695(8)
Zn(1)-S(2)	2.2601(8)	Zn(2)-S(4)	2.2676(8)	Zn(3)-S(6)	2.2781(9)
Zn(1)-N(3)	2.050(2)	Zn(2)-N(9)	2.057(2)	Zn(3)-N(15)	2.029(2)
Zn(1)-N(6)	2.040(2)	Zn(2)-N(12)	2.067(2)	Zn(3)-N(18)	2.063(2)
N(3)-Zn(1)-N(6)	120.74(8)	N(9)-Zn(2)-N(12)	101.41(8)	N(15)-Zn(3)-N(18)	115.41(9)
N(3)-Zn(1)-S(2)	119.30(6)	N(9)-Zn(2)-S(4)	130.55(6)	N(15)-Zn(3)-S(6)	126.30(7)
N(3)-Zn(1)-S(1)	86.64(6)	N(9)-Zn(2)-S(3)	86.96(6)	N(15)-Zn(3)-S(5)	87.00(6)
N(6)-Zn(1)-S(2)	87.72(6)	N(12)-Zn(2)-S(4)	86.85(6)	N(18)-Zn(3)-S(6)	86.51(6)
N(6)-Zn(1)-S(1)	120.10(6)	N(12)-Zn(2)-S(3)	132.07(6)	N(18)-Zn(3)-S(5)	122.35(7)
S(1)-Zn(1)-S(2)	126.34(3)	S(3)-Zn(2)-S(4)	122.81(3)	S(5)-Zn(3)-S(6)	123.24(3)

Experimental

The chemicals used were all of A. R. grade. Hatsc were prepared as per known method⁸. The complex was prepared by reacting alcoholic solutions of $\text{Zn}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and Hatsc in 1 : 2 molar ratio, and stirring for 2 h at 50~60°. On cooling white crystalline product was obtained. Recrystallization of the compound $\text{Zn}(\text{atsc})_2$ yielded single-crystals suitable for X-ray analysis. A transparent colorless crystal (0.50 × 0.36 × 0.32 mm) was mounted on glass fibre in a random orientation. The determination of the unit cell and the data collection were performed with MoK_α radiation ($\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$) on a Siemens P4 diffractometer equipped with a graphite crystal monochromator. A total of 8458 independent reflections were collected in the range $1.70^\circ < \theta < 25.50^\circ$ by the ω scan technique at room temperature (291 K), in which 5775 reflections with [$I \geq 2 \sigma(I)$] were considered to be observed and used in the succeeding refinement. Crystal is triclinic, space group $\text{P}\bar{1}$, with unit cell parameters : $a = 8.0530(10) \text{ \AA}$, $b = 12.233(2) \text{ \AA}$, $c = 21.476(3) \text{ \AA}$, $\alpha = 80.857(1)^\circ$, $\beta = 88.950(10)^\circ$, $\gamma = 83.010(10)^\circ$, $V = 2071.5(5) \text{ \AA}^3$, $Z = 6$, $D_c = 1.567 \text{ Mg m}^{-3}$, $\mu = 2.069 \text{ mm}^{-1}$, $F(000) = 1008$, $S = 0.978$. The structure was solved by direct methods. All hydrogen atoms were determined from successive difference Fourier syntheses. The final refinement by full-matrix least-squares with anisotropic thermal parameters for non-hydrogen atoms converged with agreement factors of $R = 0.0404$ and $wR = 0.0713$. All calculations were carried out on an IBM 486 personal computer using SHELXS86.

Acknowledgement

This project is supported by the National Natural Science Foundation of China.

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